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In situ calibrated voltammetric dissolved oxygen sensor

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Electrochemical pathways in living cells consume oxygen from the environment. On the other hand, the oxygen saturation of the extracellular environment has an enormous impact on cellular signaling. In "self-to-kill" systems and/or active implants for monitoring of dissolved oxygen for several days, weeks or even months is an important, but yet unsolved task. While Clark-type sensors are widely used for analytical purposes, the transfer of this technology to flexible micro-analytical microsystems is not straightforward [1]. These electrochemical microsystems suffer from baseline drift, disqualifying them for long-term monitoring where recalibration is not possible. Optochemical sensors are a reliable choice for many bio-analytical questions but the realization of optical microsystems still falls from the integration of the necessary optical components.

On the basis of constant amperometric measurement a defined amount of locally dissolved is periodically generated by water electrolysis using two electrodes. This additionally generated amount of oxygen is used to obtain a spatial calibration factor k , in order to correct the detector signal I_d during long-term dissolved oxygen measurements by the neighboring micro-sensor (see Figure).

Currently the sensor is integrated with microfabricated control electronics. A microcontroller runs laboratory measurements in specific operating points and releases live reads of measurement data to an external receiver unit. The whole system will be contained in a biocompatible housing. Our primary goal was to validate our approach in a biocompatible housing, where the sensor is used to monitor oxygen levels at the mucosa of the oral cavity, while our goal is to create an implantable oxygen sensor for long-term in vivo measurements within the body for tumor and brain healing.

Figure: Normalized oxygen detector current is calibrated after each cycle of oxygen generation. The area g corresponds to the generated oxygen amount.

References
[1] Bioelectrochemical structures: cell-sensor systems for applications in medicine and biotechnology. Biotechnology and Bioenergetics, 40(1999) page 219 - page 225